

Real-Time Ultrasound Brightness Correction Under Misalignment and Limited Supervision

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Abstract—Brightness mode ultrasound is strongly affected by operator-controlled gain and time-gain compensation (TGC). Incorrect settings can obscure anatomical boundaries, reduce contrast, and impair interpretability, particularly in point-of-care and educational use. This study evaluates a conservative artificial intelligence approach for real-time ultrasound brightness correction under limited supervision and residual misalignment. Instead of synthesizing a new image freely, the corrected output is constrained to be the acquired frame multiplied by a predicted gain map. Two generative adversarial network-based architectures were compared: *RetinexNet*, a higher-capacity U-Net-style model with temporal attention, and *GeoGainNet*, a lightweight geometry-aware model that factorizes log-gain into global, depth-profile, and residual components. The models were evaluated with paired multi-split experiments on a real paired carotid ultrasound benchmark and a synthetic EchoNet-derived curved-probe benchmark. Evaluation combined paired image quality, TGC-profile behavior, gain-map fidelity, anatomy preservation, temporal consistency, expert reader assessment, and CPU/GPU runtime.

On the synthetic EchoNet benchmark, both models improved 18 of 19 held-out test metrics, and all positive improvements remained significant after Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate correction. *RetinexNet* showed the stronger synthetic quality profile, outperforming *GeoGainNet* on 16 of 19 test metrics. On the real paired benchmark, *RetinexNet* improved 16 of 19 test metrics and *GeoGainNet* improved 18 of 19, with 10 and 8 false-discovery-rate-significant improvements, respectively. The direct real-data model comparison was balanced, whereas runtime strongly favored *GeoGainNet*: median GPU throughput was 294.6 frames/s versus 4.9 frames/s for *RetinexNet*, and median CPU throughput was 18.70 frames/s versus 0.24 frames/s. A single-expert reader evaluation on 15 real cases gave similar mean scores for both models. These findings support multiplicative gain-map learning as an interpretable basis for ultrasound brightness correction, while highlighting the need for larger real-data and multi-reader validation.

Index Terms—artificial intelligence, ultrasound, brightness correction, gain map, time-gain compensation, generative adversarial network, real-time inference

I. INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound is widely used in clinical and educational settings because it is safe, portable, and comparatively inexpensive relative to magnetic resonance imaging or computed tomography [1]. Its practical value depends on image quality at acquisition. In brightness mode (B-mode) ultrasound, visual appearance is strongly influenced by user-adjustable controls, especially overall gain and time-gain compensation (TGC).

Overall gain changes the global amplification of received echoes, whereas TGC changes amplification as a function of depth to compensate for acoustic attenuation. Poorly chosen settings can produce globally over-bright or under-bright images, or depth-dependent exposure imbalance in which superficial anatomy is saturated while deeper anatomy is dark, or vice versa [2].

Automatic brightness correction is clinically and technically non-trivial. Ultrasound speckle is not merely additive noise. It is a physics-based interference pattern and can carry information about tissue microstructure [3]. A correction method that maximizes visual smoothness or paired-image similarity without constraint could remove diagnostically relevant texture, alter visible boundaries, or hallucinate anatomical structure. These risks are amplified when training data are paired only approximately, as is typical for real ultrasound recordings. Even carefully repeated scans of the same anatomy differ because of probe motion, tissue deformation, breathing, and timing variation.

Prior learning-based image restoration provides useful foundations but does not directly solve the task considered here. Conditional generative adversarial networks (GANs), including pix2pix, can learn paired image-to-image mappings when aligned targets are available [4, 5]. Ultrasound-specific restoration models have addressed handheld-to-high-quality video reconstruction and related enhancement tasks [6]. Retinex-style methods motivate separating illumination-like effects from structural content [7, 8]. Work on imperfect supervision, including Noise2Noise and Speckle2Speckle, shows that restoration can be learned when ideal clean targets are unavailable [9, 10]. Simulation-based ultrasound studies further demonstrate the value of controlled synthetic data [11, 12]. However, direct automatic correction of user-induced gain and TGC errors in standard B-mode videos remains less developed, especially under real paired misalignment and real-time constraints.

The central contribution of this study is a constrained gain-map formulation for real-time ultrasound brightness correction: the model predicts how much each region of the acquired ultrasound frame should be brightened or attenuated, and the corrected image remains a multiplicatively reweighted version of the measured frame. This representation is more restrictive than unconstrained image synthesis, but it is better

aligned with the physical role of gain and TGC, exposes an interpretable intermediate output, and reduces the incentive to change anatomy in order to improve perceptual similarity.

The study evaluates two architectures under this shared formulation. *RetinexNet* is a higher-capacity temporal U-Net-style model inspired by Retinex decomposition. *GeoGainNet* is a lightweight geometry-aware model that decomposes the correction into global, depth-dependent, and residual gain components. The models are compared on two complementary data regimes: a real paired linear-probe carotid dataset and a synthetic curved-probe benchmark derived from *EchoNet-Dynamic* [13]. The paper asks whether multiplicative gain-map learning improves brightness correction, how model design affects quality and runtime, and how such systems should be evaluated when real paired data are imperfectly aligned.

The intended contribution is therefore not a generic ultrasound enhancement pipeline, but a task-specific representation and evaluation protocol for gain-related errors. The formulation deliberately separates the clinical goal, which is to improve visibility by correcting brightness, from broader image-restoration objectives such as denoising, super-resolution, or device-domain translation. This distinction shaped the experimental design. Results were interpreted only within matched data regimes, and deployment feasibility was treated as part of the method comparison rather than as a secondary implementation detail. This is important for live ultrasound, where a visually promising model that cannot operate at video rate has limited practical value.

II. METHODS

A. Brightness-correction formulation

Let

$$\mathbf{X}_t^{\text{bad}} = \{x_{t-2}^{\text{bad}}, x_{t-1}^{\text{bad}}, x_t^{\text{bad}}, x_{t+1}^{\text{bad}}, x_{t+2}^{\text{bad}}\}$$

denote a five-frame temporal window centered on a degraded B-mode frame x_t^{bad} . The paired target frame is x_t^{good} . The model predicts a multiplicative gain map $G_t \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$, and the corrected frame is

$$\hat{y}_t = x_t^{\text{bad}} \odot G_t, \quad (1)$$

where \odot denotes pointwise multiplication. The output can therefore brighten or attenuate observed pixels but cannot introduce image content independently of the acquired frame.

For *GeoGainNet*, the log-gain field is factorized as

$$\log G_t = g_t^{\text{global}} + P_t + R_t,$$

where g_t^{global} is a scalar global brightness term, P_t is a one-dimensional depth-dependent profile, and R_t is a low-resolution residual log-gain map. The factorization separates overall exposure, TGC-like depth behavior, and local refinement. In linear-probe data, depth is represented by image row. In curved-probe data, the one-dimensional profile is rendered as a function of normalized radial depth within the ultrasound sector mask.

B. Datasets

Two complementary benchmarks were used. The first was a real paired linear-probe carotid ultrasound dataset containing 15 good videos and 87 bad videos spanning 15 scenes from six different subjects, acquired on a Voluson E6 ultrasound system with an ML6-15 linear transducer at the Medical University of Vienna [14]. Each scene contained at least one well-adjusted recording and one or more degraded recordings produced by changing gain-related scanner settings while keeping probe position as stable as possible. Preprocessing included cropping of non-imaging content, resizing, manual temporal and geometric alignment, manual gain-map authoring, and extraction of five-frame windows. The paired multi-split experiment used 10 repeats with 384×512 inputs and 30–35 held-out test windows per repeat. The train/validation/test split is 80/10/10, subject to minor variation across scenes.

The real-data gain maps were not exported from scanner metadata. They were manually authored using a custom graphical interface that displayed the degraded input, current gain map, depth-versus-gain profile, corrected preview, and paired good reference. The annotation process combined a global gain control, direct manipulation of the depth profile, and local brush edits. The resulting maps should be interpreted as carefully regularized correction targets, not physical ground truth.

This distinction affects both training and interpretation. Manual gain maps encode the annotator’s estimate of an appropriate correction for a paired recording, but they cannot fully separate scanner-setting error from residual probe motion or local anatomical mismatch. The learning problem on real data is therefore approximate: the model is encouraged to predict smooth, plausible brightness compensation, while evaluation must avoid treating every pixel-level discrepancy as model error. For this reason, the real benchmark was used primarily to test whether the correction principle remained useful under realistic acquisition constraints.

The second benchmark was derived from *EchoNet-Dynamic* [13]. A subset of 500 echocardiography clips was used: 400 for training, 50 for validation, and 50 for testing. Two temporal windows were extracted per clip, yielding 800 training windows, 100 validation windows, and 100 test windows at 112×112 resolution. For each selected clip, the preprocessing pipeline estimated a sector mask and radial depth map, sampled a global gain and an eight-band TGC-like depth profile, rendered the corresponding dense gain map, and generated a degraded input by applying the sampled gain field to the original frame. The synthetic dataset included dense degradation metadata and therefore provided stronger supervision than the real paired dataset. The training split intentionally emphasized non-trivial degradations, with 31 mild, 61 medium, and 308 strong clips.

The synthetic benchmark was not treated as a replacement for real ultrasound validation. It served a different role: controlled measurement of whether each architecture could learn the intended gain field when alignment, mask, depth, and

Visualization of GeoGainNets Decomposition

Fig. 1. Gain-map decomposition used by GeoGainNet. The effective multiplicative correction field combines a global gain term, a depth-dependent profile term, and a local residual term before being applied to the measured input frame.

degradation metadata were known. Its curved-probe geometry also tested whether the representation could move beyond the row-wise depth assumption used for linear probes. Because the real and synthetic benchmarks differed in anatomy, geometry, resolution, and supervision quality, cross-dataset numerical comparisons were interpreted descriptively rather than as direct domain-transfer evidence.

C. Model architectures

Both generators predicted a gain map that was applied to the center frame, and both were trained with a local PatchGAN discriminator [5]. RetinexNet was the higher-capacity model. It processed the five-frame temporal window with a four-level U-Net-style encoder using dual convolution blocks, instance normalization, and LeakyReLU activations. Bottleneck features from neighboring frames were fused with multi-head self-attention [15]. A dedicated gain head predicted a dense gain field, constrained to $[0.5, 2.0]$, which was smoothed before application. In linear-probe configuration, the model biased the gain toward a depth-only TGC profile by averaging and smoothing across image rows. In curved-probe configuration, this row-wise bias was disabled.

GeoGainNet was designed for deployment efficiency and interpretability. It used mobile-style depthwise-separable convolutional blocks inspired by efficient convolutional architectures [16]. The channel widths were 24, 40, 64, and 80. A shared bottleneck fed three heads: a global-gain head, a one-dimensional profile head, and a residual-map head. The profile head predicted an eight-bin depth profile corresponding conceptually to TGC slider behavior. The combined log-gain was clamped to $[-0.65, 0.65]$, exponentiated, and clipped to the same final gain range $[0.5, 2.0]$ as RetinexNet.

The discriminator consisted of three spectral-normalized strided 3×3 convolutional blocks followed by a spectral-normalized 1×1 logit layer. It returned patch-level logits rather than a single global score. The adversarial component supplied local texture pressure, while supervised reconstruction and gain losses drove the primary correction behavior.

D. Training protocol

All runs used the same optimization protocol. Models were trained for 40 epochs with batch size 2, gradient clipping at norm 1.0, and exponential moving average evaluation of generator weights with decay 0.999. The generator and discriminator were optimized with AdamW [17]. Learning rates were 3×10^{-4} for the generator and 5×10^{-5} for the discriminator, with $\beta_1 = 0.5$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, and weight decay 10^{-4} .

The generator objective combined several loss groups. Image-similarity losses compared the corrected frame with the paired good frame using local patch L_1 , structural similarity, gradient-correlation, differentiable histogram, shallow perceptual, and scanline brightness-profile terms. Gain supervision used masked mean absolute error between predicted and reference gain maps, with cone restriction for curved data. Anisotropic total variation penalized implausible high-frequency gain oscillations, with stronger lateral or tangential smoothing than depth-wise or radial smoothing. Temporal losses weakly penalized frame-to-frame changes and depth-profile drift across the five-frame corrected window. The discriminator used least-squares GAN losses, one-sided label smoothing, random label flips with probability 0.03, and input noise annealing during the first 10 epochs. The adversarial weight was zero for the first 5 epochs and ramped to 0.01 over the next 5 epochs.

The implementation used Python ≥ 3.10 , PyTorch ≥ 2.1 , and torchvision ≥ 0.16 [18]. GPU training and inference measurements were performed on Kaggle with two NVIDIA T4 GPUs [19]. Additional CPU inference measurements used a laptop with an AMD Ryzen 7 PRO 4750U CPU and 32 GB RAM.

E. Evaluation and statistical analysis

Evaluation was organized as a paired multi-split comparison. For each split repeat, RetinexNet and GeoGainNet were trained and evaluated on the same partitions. The split repeat, not the individual frame, was treated as the statistical

TABLE I
 PAIRED MULTI-SPLIT EXPERIMENT OVERVIEW. BOTH BENCHMARKS USED FIVE-FRAME TEMPORAL WINDOWS, DIRECT GAIN SUPERVISION, AND THE STRICT MULTIPLICATIVE CORRECTION FORMULATION IN EQUATION 1.

Dataset	Geometry	Resolution	Paired repeats	Test windows per repeat
Real paired carotid	Linear	384×512	10	30–35
EchoNet synthetic	Curved	112×112	10	100

unit to avoid inflated significance from pooled frame-level metrics [20]. For every metric, sample-level values were converted to signed symmetric relative improvement over the degraded input:

$$r = \frac{2\sigma(q_{\text{enhanced}} - q_{\text{bad}})}{|q_{\text{enhanced}}| + |q_{\text{bad}}| + \varepsilon},$$

where $\sigma = 1$ for metrics where larger values are better, $\sigma = -1$ for metrics where smaller values are better, and $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$. Positive values therefore indicate improvement regardless of metric direction. Improvements were summarized at run level before inference.

The metric set covered paired image quality (L_1 , SSIM, PSNR, patch and masked variants), depth-dependent brightness behavior (E_{TGC} , TGC correlation, and Δ_{TGC}), gain fidelity (MAE_G, RMSE_G, log-domain and profile variants), anatomy preservation, temporal consistency, clip-level distributional behavior, and inference speed. Structural similarity, Wasserstein histogram distance, normalized mutual information, and Fréchet-style distribution distance followed established uses in image-quality and generative-model evaluation [21–24]. Anatomy metrics were interpreted cautiously on real paired data because target frames were not perfectly aligned.

Depth-profile and gain-fidelity metrics were central to the evaluation because the desired behavior is not simply to make the corrected frame look more like the paired target. E_{TGC} measured the mismatch between normalized depth-brightness profiles of the corrected and reference frames, while Δ_{TGC} measured whether the corrected profile moved closer to the reference than the degraded input. Gain-map errors measured whether the predicted multiplicative field matched the intended correction itself. These metrics were complemented by input- and target-anchored anatomy scores. The input-anchored variants are especially relevant on real data because they ask whether the measured anatomy visible in the degraded frame remains stable after correction.

For direct model comparisons, paired run-level deltas were tested with the Wilcoxon signed-rank test when at least two non-zero paired deltas were available [25]. Otherwise, an exact two-sided sign test was used. Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction was applied across metric families [26]. The threshold for FDR significance was $q_{\text{BH}} < 0.0500$. A single ultrasound expert also evaluated 15 real-data cases descriptively on five ordinal 1–5 questions. This reader assessment was not used for hypothesis testing.

III. RESULTS

A. Within-model improvement

Both architectures improved the degraded inputs on most metrics (Table II). On the real paired benchmark, RetinexNet improved 16 of 19 held-out test metrics and GeoGainNet improved 18 of 19. After FDR correction, 10 of 19 RetinexNet improvements and 8 of 19 GeoGainNet improvements remained significant. Significant real-data rows for RetinexNet included E_{TGC} ($q_{\text{BH}} = 0.0046$), Δ_{TGC} ($q_{\text{BH}} = 0.0070$), MAE_G ($q_{\text{BH}} = 0.0070$), and RMSE_G ($q_{\text{BH}} = 0.0070$). These results indicate reproducible improvements in several brightness- and gain-related criteria, although the evidence was less uniform than in the synthetic setting. The corresponding real-data run-level distributions are shown in Fig. 2.

On the EchoNet benchmark, both model families improved 18 of 19 test metrics. All 18 positive centers remained significant after FDR correction for both RetinexNet and GeoGainNet. The only test metric without a positive across-run center was the general gradient-correlation metric. The stronger consistency on EchoNet is expected because synthetic degradation provides exact frame correspondence and dense gain metadata.

B. Direct model comparison

The model-level comparison depended strongly on dataset (Table III). On the real paired test split, GeoGainNet had the better across-run center for 10 of 19 metrics, and RetinexNet had the better center for 9 of 19. The selected real-data quality deltas did not remain significant after FDR correction. For example, the L_1 improvement was 0.0302 for RetinexNet and 0.0468 for GeoGainNet, with $\Delta_{\text{Geo-Ret}} = 0.0166$ and $q_{\text{BH}} = 0.6590$. The SSIM improvement was 0.0097 and 0.0234, respectively, with $q_{\text{BH}} = 0.2800$. RetinexNet had the higher E_{TGC} improvement on the real benchmark (0.1989 versus 0.1230), but the paired model difference was not significant ($q_{\text{BH}} = 1.0000$). GeoGainNet had the higher MAE_G improvement (0.2966 versus 0.2510), again without significant model difference ($q_{\text{BH}} = 0.9130$).

On EchoNet, the quality comparison favored RetinexNet. It had the better center for 16 of 19 test metrics and 18 of 19 validation metrics. Selected model deltas all favored RetinexNet: L_1 by 0.1086, SSIM by 0.0092, E_{TGC} by 0.2383, MAE_G by 0.2009, and $\text{NMI}_A^{\text{tar}}$ by 0.0501. These selected EchoNet differences all had $q_{\text{BH}} = 0.0026$, indicating reproducible quality advantages for the larger model under controlled synthetic supervision.

TABLE II

WITHIN-MODEL IMPROVEMENT SUMMARY ACROSS 10 PAIRED SPLIT REPEATS. A METRIC WAS COUNTED AS IMPROVED WHEN ITS ACROSS-RUN CENTER OF SIGNED RELATIVE IMPROVEMENT WAS POSITIVE. THE CORE SUBSET EXCLUDES ANATOMY METRICS AND FID, BECAUSE ANATOMY SCORES SHOULD REMAIN CLOSE TO THE INPUT UNDER STRUCTURE-PRESERVING CORRECTION AND FID WAS TREATED AS A SECONDARY DISTRIBUTIONAL CHECK.

Dataset	Model	Test improvements			Validation
		Metrics	FDR-significant	Core FDR-significant	Metrics improved
Real	RetinexNet	16/19	10/19	8/15	16/19
Real	GeoGainNet	18/19	8/19	8/15	17/19
EchoNet	RetinexNet	18/19	18/19	14/15	18/19
EchoNet	GeoGainNet	18/19	18/19	14/15	18/19

Cross-Run Metric Behavior (Real Dataset)

Fig. 2. Within-model improvement distributions on the real paired benchmark. Panel a reports the run-level median signed relative improvement. Panel b reports the run-level interquartile range (IQR). Values above zero indicate improvement over the degraded input. Lower IQR values indicate more consistent per-run behavior.

C. Runtime

Runtime strongly favored GeoGainNet. On the real paired benchmark, median GPU throughput was 294.6 frames/s for GeoGainNet and 4.9 frames/s for RetinexNet. Median CPU throughput was 18.70 frames/s and 0.24 frames/s, respectively. The corresponding median real-data inference times were 3.7 ms versus 202.5 ms on GPU and 53.5 ms versus 4200.9 ms on CPU. On EchoNet, median GPU throughput

was 179.6 frames/s for GeoGainNet and 50.9 frames/s for RetinexNet. Median CPU throughput was 71.8 frames/s and 2.6 frames/s. Median EchoNet inference times were 5.9 ms versus 19.9 ms on GPU and 14.7 ms versus 385.7 ms on CPU. The selected GPU throughput deltas were significant after FDR correction on both datasets.

Example of Brightness Correction (Real Dataset)

Example of Brightness Correction (EchoNet Dataset)

Fig. 3. Representative qualitative brightness-correction examples for the real paired carotid benchmark (top) and synthetic EchoNet benchmark (bottom). In each panel, the degraded input is shown with reference and predicted gain maps and corrected outputs. Brighter gain-map regions indicate stronger brightening.

TABLE III

SELECTED PAIRED MODEL COMPARISONS ON HELD-OUT TEST SPLITS. QUALITY, GAIN, AND ANATOMY ROWS REPORT SIGNED RELATIVE IMPROVEMENTS OVER THE DEGRADED INPUT, SO LARGER VALUES ARE BETTER. $\Delta_{\text{Geo}-\text{Ret}}$ IS GEOGAINNET MINUS RETINEXNET . POSITIVE VALUES FAVOR GEOGAINNET , NEGATIVE VALUES FAVOR RETINEXNET . FPS_{inf} REPORTS GPU THROUGHPUT IN FRAMES PER SECOND.

Dataset	Metric	RetinexNet	GeoGainNet	$\Delta_{\text{Geo}-\text{Ret}}$	Geo better	q_{BH}
Real	L_1	0.0302	0.0468	0.0166	7/10	0.6590
Real	SSIM	0.0097	0.0234	0.0138	8/10	0.2800
Real	E_{TGC}	0.1989	0.1230	-0.0759	5/10	1.0000
Real	MAE_G	0.2510	0.2966	0.0456	6/10	0.9130
Real	$\rho_{\nabla, A}^{\text{tar}}$	-0.0092	0.0000	0.0092	6/10	0.9130
Real	$\text{NMI}_A^{\text{tar}}$	-0.0205	0.0115	0.0320	8/10	0.2800
Real	FPS_{inf}	4.9	294.6	289.6	10/10	0.0449
EchoNet	L_1	0.5610	0.4524	-0.1086	0/10	0.0026
EchoNet	SSIM	0.0499	0.0407	-0.0092	0/10	0.0026
EchoNet	E_{TGC}	0.7571	0.5187	-0.2383	0/10	0.0026
EchoNet	MAE_G	0.7627	0.5619	-0.2009	0/10	0.0026
EchoNet	$\rho_{\nabla, A}^{\text{tar}}$	0.0007	0.0002	-0.0005	0/10	0.0026
EchoNet	$\text{NMI}_A^{\text{tar}}$	0.1143	0.0642	-0.0501	0/10	0.0026
EchoNet	FPS_{inf}	50.9	179.6	128.7	10/10	0.0026

Fig. 4. Model-delta distributions on held-out test splits for the real paired and EchoNet benchmarks. Positive values indicate larger signed relative improvement for GeoGainNet. Negative values indicate larger improvement for RetinexNet.

D. Expert reader evaluation

A single ultrasound expert evaluated 15 real-data cases using five ordinal 1–5 criteria. The expert compared each enhanced output with the bad input and the corresponding good-settings reference. Scores were descriptive only because one

reader was available. Mean overall improvement was 3.87 ± 1.36 for RetinexNet and 4.00 ± 1.00 for GeoGainNet. Mean overall gain was 4.00 ± 1.20 and 3.67 ± 1.23 , respectively. Mean TGC/depth-brightness scores were 3.64 ± 1.22 for RetinexNet and 3.60 ± 1.24 for GeoGainNet. One

Fig. 5. CPU and GPU inference throughput on held-out test splits. Higher values indicate faster processing. GeoGainNet consistently achieved higher throughput than RetinexNet, with the largest deployment-relevant advantage on the real paired benchmark.

RetinexNet answer was omitted for this criterion. Anatomy preservation scores were 4.67 ± 0.82 and 4.73 ± 0.70 , and speckle-realism scores were 4.27 ± 1.53 and 4.33 ± 1.45 .

Across all five questions, the pooled mean score was 4.09 for RetinexNet and 4.07 for GeoGainNet. The pooled median was 5 for both methods. Favorable ratings, defined as scores of at least 4, occurred in 57 of 74 available RetinexNet ratings and 56 of 75 GeoGainNet ratings. At the case level, after averaging criteria within each case, GeoGainNet was higher in 6 cases, RetinexNet was higher in 7, and 2 cases were tied. One free-text comment described some outputs as having an unrealistic gray veil, indicating that occasional perceptual failures remained.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results support multiplicative gain-map learning as a technically sound formulation for ultrasound brightness correction. The main conceptual advantage is that correction remains tied to the measured B-mode frame. This is important because the task is not anatomical reconstruction. A model should reduce brightness-related defects while preserving visible structures and speckle appearance. Equation 1 enforces that bias directly: the output can only reweight the input.

The strongest quantitative evidence comes from the synthetic EchoNet benchmark. Both architectures improved 18 of 19 held-out test metrics, and all positive improvements remained significant after FDR correction. The magnitude of selected effects was also substantial. RetinexNet improved L_1 by 56.1%, SSIM by 5.0%, E_{TGC} by 75.7%, and MAE_G by 76.3%. GeoGainNet reached 45.2%, 4.1%, 51.9%, and 56.2% on the same metrics. These results show that the

multiplicative representation can recover controlled global and depth-dependent degradation patterns when dense supervision and exact pairing are available.

The real paired benchmark provides more clinically relevant but more uncertain evidence. RetinexNet improved 16 of 19 test metrics and GeoGainNet improved 18 of 19. Selected real-data improvements included E_{TGC} reductions of 19.9% and 12.3%, and MAE_G reductions of 25.1% and 29.7%, for RetinexNet and GeoGainNet, respectively. The direct real-data model comparison was balanced: GeoGainNet was ahead on 10 of 19 metrics and RetinexNet on 9 of 19. None of the selected real-data quality differences remained significant after FDR correction. This is consistent with the single-expert evaluation, in which both models received similar mean scores and favorable preservation ratings.

The dataset-dependent model comparison is informative. Under controlled synthetic supervision, RetinexNet was the stronger quality model, likely because its higher-capacity temporal U-Net and attention bottleneck could exploit exact alignment and dense gain metadata. In the real paired benchmark, where supervision was approximate and residual mismatch remained, the quality advantage disappeared. This does not mean that the larger model failed. Rather, the evidence suggests that model capacity alone is not sufficient when target correspondence and gain labels are uncertain. The lightweight GeoGainNet remained competitive on realistic data while providing a clearer gain decomposition and much stronger runtime.

Runtime is the clearest practical distinction. GeoGainNet reached 294.6 frames/s on GPU and 18.70 frames/s on CPU on the real paired benchmark, compared with 4.9 and

0.24 frames/s for RetinexNet. On EchoNet, GeoGainNet also remained faster on both devices. These results make GeoGainNet the more plausible deployment candidate for live or near-real-time systems, especially when a dedicated GPU cannot be assumed. The interpretability of its global, depth-profile, and residual components is also useful for education and quality-control workflows, where users may benefit from seeing the predicted correction rather than only the corrected image.

The study also shows why ultrasound brightness correction should not be evaluated with a single metric family. Paired image quality metrics are necessary, but they can reward target matching even when the target is misaligned. Gain-fidelity and TGC-profile metrics test whether the model has learned the intended correction mechanism. Anatomy-preservation metrics help identify whether structure changes are introduced, but target-anchored anatomy metrics are difficult to interpret on real paired data because probe motion and temporal mismatch can lower target agreement even when input anatomy is preserved. Input-anchored preservation, temporal stability, runtime, and expert assessment are therefore important complements.

These findings are consistent with the broader restoration literature while also defining a narrower task. General image-to-image translation can be powerful when paired targets are well aligned [5], but this flexibility is not automatically desirable in ultrasound brightness correction. The Retinex-inspired view is more appropriate because gain and TGC act as multiplicative exposure fields rather than as new anatomical content [7, 8]. The results also align with the lesson from weakly supervised and synthetic ultrasound restoration: controlled supervision can demonstrate feasibility, but real-data validation remains necessary before clinical claims are made [10, 12]. The present study adds that runtime and interpretability should be evaluated alongside quality, because post-processing must be usable during video acquisition or review.

Several limitations constrain interpretation. First, the real paired dataset was small. Ten paired split repeats reduce dependence on a single partition, but they do not replace a larger multicenter dataset. Second, real paired recordings were only approximately aligned. Residual motion, deformation, breathing, and timing differences affect both training and evaluation. Third, the real-data gain maps were manually authored correction targets rather than scanner-exported ground truth. Fourth, the real and synthetic benchmarks differed in multiple factors simultaneously, including anatomy, probe geometry, image resolution, alignment quality, and supervision quality. Differences between benchmarks therefore cannot be attributed to one isolated cause. Fifth, the expert reader evaluation used one expert and 15 cases. It provides clinical plausibility evidence but not inter-rater reliability, diagnostic accuracy, or downstream task validation. Finally, runtime measurements show strong model-level speed differences but do not constitute a complete deployment study with ultrasound hardware integration, memory profiling, latency budgeting,

and user-interface evaluation.

Future work should expand the real paired dataset across devices, operators, anatomical regions, and patient populations. Scanner-exported gain and TGC metadata, where available, would help separate model error from annotation uncertainty. If scanner metadata are unavailable, multiple annotators and inter-rater agreement analysis would strengthen manual gain-map supervision. Evaluation under misalignment should also be improved through registration-aware, uncertainty-aware, and input-anchored metrics validated against expert judgment. Clinically, a multi-reader study should test perceived image quality, anatomical visibility, speckle realism, diagnostic confidence, and downstream task performance. From a model-development perspective, GeoGainNet could be extended with stronger temporal regularization or uncertainty estimates, whereas RetinexNet could be compressed or distilled to combine synthetic-benchmark quality with practical throughput.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that real-time ultrasound brightness correction can be formulated as interpretable multiplicative gain-map prediction. The approach improves controlled synthetic degradations strongly and shows promising real-data performance despite limited supervision and residual misalignment. RetinexNet provides the stronger quality profile under synthetic supervision, while GeoGainNet is faster, more interpretable, and competitive on real paired data. The method should be viewed as a technically validated brightness-correction approach with initial clinical plausibility support, not yet as a fully clinically validated diagnostic system.

V. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Martin Stasek led study conception, data collection, implementation, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. Matthias Blaickner supervised the research process, provided conceptual guidance, and critically reviewed and revised the manuscript. Christian Kollmann supported video recording at the Medical University of Vienna and provided guidance on the research topic.

VI. CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

VII. DATA AVAILABILITY

The synthetic benchmark was derived from the EchoNet-Dynamic dataset cited in this manuscript. The project source code and supporting materials are available at <https://github.com/mastrich00/Ultrasound-Brightness-Correction-GAN>. The real paired carotid ultrasound recordings and manual gain maps are not publicly distributed and may be requested by contacting the authors, subject to institutional approval and applicable data-use conditions.

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